

**BRAND PERSONALITY AND CONSUMER SATISFACTION
FROM GUINNESS IN CAMEROON: TWO MEASURES BY
ONE CONSTRUCT, EMOTION AND GRATIFICATION**

**PERSONNALITE DE LA MARQUE ET SATISFACTION DU
CONSOMMATEUR : DEUX MESURES PAR UN CONSTRUIT,
L'EMOTION ET LA GRATIFICATION**

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Abstract

Nowadays, brands are a very important part of our society. They are only multiplying, thereby creating general confusion in the minds of consumers, which forces companies to seek a differentiated positioning on the market. This study aims to analyze the explanatory power of brand personality on consumer satisfaction through emotion and gratification. Using a quantitative approach, a survey conducted among a large sample of consumers of the Guinness brand in Cameroon made it possible to test and verify the various research hypotheses using regression analyses. Thus, the result obtained highlights the direct influence of brand personality on satisfaction as well as its predictive power on consumer emotion and gratification. However, it highlights the interest for managers to take into consideration the concept of brand personality in the management of their brands.

Keywords: “Brand personality”; “satisfaction”; “relationship with the brand”; “consumer”; “Guinness”

Résumé

De nos jours, les marques constituent un élément très important de notre société. Elles ne font que se multiplier, créant par là même une confusion générale dans l’esprit des consommateurs, ce qui contraint les entreprises à rechercher un positionnement différencié sur le marché. Cette étude vise à analyser le pouvoir explicatif de la personnalité de la marque sur satisfaction du consommateur à travers l’émotion et la gratification. A partir d’une approche quantitative, une enquête menée auprès d’un échantillon conséquent des consommateurs de la marque Guinness au Cameroun a permis de tester et de vérifier grâce à des analyses de régression les différentes hypothèses de la recherche. Ainsi, le résultat obtenu met en évidence l’influence directe de la personnalité de la marque sur la satisfaction ainsi que son pouvoir prédictif sur l’émotion et la gratification du consommateur. Toutefois, elle souligne l’intérêt pour les managers de prendre en considération le concept de personnalité de la marque dans la gestion de leurs marques.

Mots clés : « Personnalité de la marque » ; « satisfaction » ; « relation à la marque » ; « consommateur » ; « Guinness »

Introduction

Nowadays, brands present an important issue for businesses. They continue to increase, thereby creating general confusion in the minds of consumers, which forces companies to seek a differentiated positioning on the market (Rita & Valette-Florence, 2020). Thus, it is difficult for a company to stay in the market for such a long time by focusing only on the tangible aspects of its product. These companies increasingly need to define a position on the market based on intangible attributes of the product, such as the brand. Thus, company strategies are oriented in most cases on brands and not the product itself in question. Thus, several studies have been carried out in this area and this in different sectors such as drinks (Cindy & Lombart, 2013), perfumes (Ambroise, 2010), shopping centers (Lichtlé & Plichon, 2014) or tourism (Hosany and al., 2015). Moreover, the work of d'Aaker (1993) is fundamental to this trend on brand personality. Several companies see it to a certain extent as a real instrument for customer satisfaction and loyalty. The point here is to know what is really the link that the consumer has with the brands they consume? Overall, does the personality of a brand help explain consumer behavior, particularly satisfaction? To this end, we focus on the following research question: "Does brand personality improve consumer satisfaction?" It is therefore from this perspective that we considered it important to better understand the mechanism by which the personality of a brand predicts consumer satisfaction with brands while maintaining continuity with previous work. This research attempts to study consumer behavior from the angle of satisfaction through emotion and gratification.

As part of this research, we attempt to understand and better explain consumer behavior through the differences that exist between individuals. To this end, this study attempts to analyze the direct effects of brand personality on satisfaction through emotion and gratification. This study is not part of a logic of discovery, but rather of a logic of confirmation. It is based on previous research in order to propose a model making it possible to highlight the mechanisms which condition consumer behavior, in particular satisfaction. Furthermore, our approach is indeed a cause and effect approach. We will try to find a relationship between the phenomena studied and reconstruct a chain of causes and effects linking the personality of the brand to consumer satisfaction. To complete and nourish this theoretical reflection, we examined the practices of Cameroonian consumers.

Our research is structured around three main parts. First a review of the literature and the hypotheses are presented. Then, the methodology approach will be discussed and finally a discussion of the results obtained as well as a conclusion will be the subject of this last part.

1. Literature review and research hypotheses

Studying consumer behavior means seeking to understand the process of perception and evaluation of the various elements of an acquisition (El-gozmir & Chouhbi, 2023). Brand personality is one of the fields of investigation that is widely studied in marketing (Rolland, 1993). It is obvious from the start that the acquisition of a product or brand does not only depend on the purchasing decision but also on the nature of the offer itself (Lakhlili, 2017). Personality guides the consumer by directing the behavior chosen to achieve the objectives specific to different situations (Aaker, 1997). On a purely operational level, understanding the relationships that individuals have with the brands of the products they consume may not only be interesting in defining the strategic orientations of the company (Albert and al., 2017) but also in continuous improvement in consumer satisfaction (Housni, 2022). First of all, the definitions proposed by the researchers, then the main theories relating to the personality of the individual will be discussed and finally, the elements allowing a better understanding of it will be highlighted.

1.1. Origin and definition of brand personality

From an etiological point of view, the word “personality” goes back to Latin or theological roots whose meanings are multiple (Sohier, 2002). Coming from the psychoanalytic theory of Sigmund Freud, personality is considered as a whole made up of organized elements which underlies the behavior of the being (Rogers, 1968). It can only be defined in terms of an individual's reactions towards other people in recurring interpersonal situations in life (Sirgy, 1982). A summary of the definitions proposed by researchers are grouped in table 1 below:

Table N°1: Some definitions of human personality

Author	Définition
Funder, (2001)	« A particular combination of an individual's thoughts, emotions and behaviors, linked by psychological mechanisms, hidden or not, which determine this combination »
Huteau (1985)	«A stable and individualized unit of pipe assembly
Triandis et Suh (2002).	« A configuration of cognitions, emotions and skills activated when situations stimulate their expression»
Cattel (1950)	«Anything that allows a prediction of what a person will do in a given situation»
Allport (1973)	«It is a dynamic organization within individuals, a psychological system which determines their behavior and thoughts»

Source: adapted from Azoulay & Kapferer (2003)

Thus, because of the complexity of the notion of personality, no definition allows us to better understand personality. Each focuses on a different aspect of personality, but the definitions developed below only present certain general characteristics of personality. Personality is a psychological concept whose bases are physiological. It is also an internal force that determines the way in which individuals will behave (Goldberg & Saucier, 1995).

1.2. The notion of trait and the transposition of the concept of personality to the field of brands

Hirschman et Holbrook (1982), in their work entitled “*Hedonic consumption*” provide us with more details on the question of the transposition of this concept to the field of brands. Studies on brand personality have partly guided the debate on the possibility of transposing this concept to the field of brands. The doubt regarding the handling of this concept then lies in the acceptance of this term in marketing in relation to the metaphor relating to the concept of brand.

1.2.1. The theory of traits and the foundation of human personality

Originally, the definition of a trait was given by Allport (1936). According to Becheur et al. (2017), the traits measured are static variables, useful for describing what a person is or for predicting important behaviors, but very little relevant for having a better understanding of personality processes and dynamics. Traits are generally and personalized, consistent and stable tendencies of an individual to adjust to their environment (De Raad & Szirmk, 1994). Over time, other definitions have been proposed; this is now widely accepted: a “trait” can be

defined as any state that is sufficiently specific and durable to differentiate an individual from others (Lehman, 1999). These dimensions correspond to several traits through social interactions (Ostendorf & Angleitner, 1994). These traits, (products of indifference) and (hypothetical construction), make it possible to describe the human personality (De Montmollin, 1965). Thus, if the theory therefore refers to the idea of traits that can be represented by markers, it seems important to understand concretely how these markers are identified and characterized (Ambroise, 2006). Rolland (1993) emphasizes that the differences between individuals considered to have any utility in the regulation of social interactions were recorded in symbolic form in a language. Thus, the distinctive characteristic of the lexical approach is the identification and organization of a lexical universe of traits which also refer to individual references at the level of personality attributes (Goldberg & Saucier, 1995). The point here lies in the legitimacy of the transposition of this concept to the field of brands (Batazzi & Parizot, 2016).

1.2.2. Other theories relating to human personality

Studies on human personality group this concept into major recognized categories such as psychoanalytic theory, trait theory, phenomenological theory and cognitive theory (Davies & al., 2001). These theories are briefly presented in the paragraphs below.

❖ Psychoanalytic theory

Sigmund Freud was the pioneer of this theory. Freud started from the sexual drives that human beings exert on the personality (Mac Crae & Costa, 1982). In fact, according to the author, individuals are in a permanent quest for pleasure and therefore constitute an energy system. These researchers emphasize that Freud thinks that the individual is constantly in search of personal pleasure. According to Becheur and al., (2017), Freud studied the typologies of individuals based on the dynamic and structural foundations of human personality. As mentioned by McCrae (1982), the latter studied being from the angle of the id, the ego and the superego which dominate each other as much as the perception of the other is inscribed in the system of otherness and representation (Ettien and al., 2022). This work allowed him to obtain three categories of individuals which he describes as erotic, obsessive and narcissistic.

❖ The phenomenological theory

Unlike psychoanalytic theory, phenomenological theory attempts to study the individual as well as the world around them (Roger, 1968). This researcher started from animist theory to better understand the mechanism that conditions human reality. More precisely, it is a question

of the fundamental notions of the id, the ego and the I. Here, the author explains the reduction of tensions contrary to the work of Freud. Just as behaviorist theory stipulates, human behavior results from the interaction between the individual and their environment (Nifaoui, 2020). Thus, consumer behaviors are studied by examining environmental stimuli that lead to specific behavioral responses where perception plays a key role in the purchasing behavior of individuals (Carrel et al., 2023).

In order to better understand the concept of personality, this theory will be supplemented by cognitive theory.

❖ **Cognitive theory**

This theory focuses on the process of processing information by individuals in the broad sense of the term (Rolland, 1993). Indeed, the author underlines the interest given to the way in which information is stored and then processed by the subject. According to him, individuals observe phenomena and study them in order to predict the future (Carrel and al., 2023). Information therefore appears to be an element in the construction of an individual's personality. Let us remember once again that until now, there has been no ideal definition of personality. It is understood as being a more or less stable and individualized unity of thought, emotion and behavior (Rolland, 199). However, it is important to note that it is difficult to determine an individual's personality based on individual differences. In the following paragraph, we will address the legitimacy of the transposition of the concept of personality to the field of brands.

1.2.3. The transposition of the human personality into the domain of brands

There are numerous researchers in the transposition of personality traits to the field of brands (Ambroie, 2010; Cindy & Lombard, 2013; Rita & valette-Florence, 2020). According to Digman (1990), the word brand is actually a metaphor. It is a social representation and an element of belief and symbols socially shared by individuals in a society. Talking about personality and its transposition to the field of brands requires highlighting the conceptual metaphor. Cornelissen (2003) defends the idea that a metaphor should respect the criterion of isomorphism and the heuristic value of comparison. Precisely, there must be a real analogy between the attributes of the two phenomena or the two subjects which is however more understandable thanks to the notion of personality trait (Cornelissen, 2003). So, saying that a person is jealous refers to a personality trait. Individuals interpret the actions of others more than they simply react to them; it is through this interpretation that the personality then takes shape (Ambroise, 2010). In this case, we think that symbols play a mediating role in the

relationships that individuals have with physical reality, whether it refers to abstract or concrete objects (Ambroise, 2010). This process can take three forms: deduction, induction and abduction (Funder, 1980). Indeed, in daily life, individuals carry out several activities, gestures, movements, etc. which in reality reflect the stability of references. Also, like individuals, the brand embodies a personality which can sometimes be assimilated to that of an individual. To say that a drink is powerful is to express its personality. Much like human personality, this stability and durability does not refute the existence of a certain evolution of brand personality, but rather supports that there is continuity in evolution (Funder, 2001). Companies tend to increasingly improve the attributes of their brands to better position themselves in the market (Maignan & al, 2020). Also, a good brand image helps strengthen the link between a brand and the consumer (El hamidini, 2022). In addition, the adoption of a brand strategy strengthens the image of this brand and therefore strengthens consumer satisfaction and loyalty (Hoeffler & Keller, 2020). In view of all of the above, the transposition of the human personality to the domain of brands is therefore legitimate. The following paragraph will introduce the concept of consumer satisfaction.

1.3. The concept of consumer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is reflected by their behavior. Studies carried out in this area show that a satisfied customer tends to repeat the purchase. He becomes more attached to the brand or the point of sale (Nacera, 2021). Consumer satisfaction can be better captured from attributes such as cognitive state, emotional reaction, evaluation of the consumption process and judgment (Monglo & Taningbé, 2021). In the process of customer transformation, from his transition from the suspicious state to the adept state, the consumer goes through a process of building the link between him and his favorite brand. Thus, in this paragraph, we will define satisfaction and present the different approaches related to it within the framework of this study.

1.3.1. Definitions of satisfaction

Oliver (1980), understands satisfaction as being “an overall evaluation carried out after a choice concerning a specific purchasing decision”. Several researchers have demonstrated the significant impact of brand personality on consumer satisfaction. The perceived value of a brand has a significant impact on consumer satisfaction (Ouaddi & Tamanine, 2020). According to these authors, it corresponds to a global evaluation of the response of “everything” to a previously felt need. Furthermore, research on satisfaction has not yet

reached a real consensus to define this concept (Abba & Halidou, 2020). It is a conative process resulting from a consumption experience (Ltifi & Hikkerova, 2018). Indeed, satisfaction can be understood as a phenomenon that is not directly observable, resulting from both a dual cognitive and affective process (Oliver, 1980). In the context of this research, the components of satisfaction are essentially gratification and the emotion of consumption.

1.3.2. The components of satisfaction

According to Oliver (1980), the cognitive attribute of consumer satisfaction relates to the level of satisfaction felt by the latter, to the measure of the concordance of the prior expectation and the actual consumption experience or to the assessment of the state of gratification (Oliver, 1997). In other words, consumer satisfaction comes down to the feeling of reward regarding the consumer's expectations and their needs, promoting purchasing intention (Maghraoui & Belghith, 2021). It is therefore a cognitive judgment of the individual on the gratification obviously accompanies the emotional reaction. This research is in line with this.

❖ Gratification

To better understand the meaning of “*gratification*”, we must refer to the word “satisfy” which means: “to gratify to the point of being sufficiently fulfilled” (Oliver, 1980). In addition, it must be analyzed according to certain criteria insofar as it presupposes the existence of an objective (Oliver, 1997) which is broken down into “satisfaction of expectations” or “satisfaction of needs”. A priori, let us recall that the concept of expectation linked to consumer satisfaction derives from the very popular model of Oliver's (1980) expectation disconfirmation paradigm, according to which it is important for the consumer to evaluate to what extent the product/service provides particular benefits or produces expected performance. According to this paradigm, the consumer feels satisfaction to the extent that the actual performance of the product corresponds to or exceeds the level of expectation (Akkarene and al., 2021). Whether it is predictive expectation or the consumer's evaluation of what the product offers in terms of benefits or expected performance, it should be noted that the paradigm of disconfirmation of expectations explains with perfect rigor scientific, the concept of satisfaction (Oliver, 1980; El-amidine, 2022). Let us remember that the consumer will seek to evaluate the extent to which the performance of the product/service gratifies his need, which plays a reference role in judging the latter's gratification.

❖ The emotion of consumption

The formation of consumer satisfaction is a two-step process based on the moment of purchase: pre-purchase process and post-purchase process (Oliver, 1997). In the process before purchasing, the consumer expects the performance of the product based on various information. In the post-purchase process, the latter judges that the expectation and the need which arose before the act of purchase are well gratified. Finally, he makes his judgment on satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Indeed, in accordance with the theory of cognitive evaluation of emotion, the consumer who perceives the level of gratification of the expectation and the need feels the state of balance and instantly manifests an emotional reaction, however leading to true loyalty. (Oliver & Linda, 1981). Consumption emotion is, in other words, the effect of cognitive evaluation on the consumption experience (Rita & Florence-Florence, 2020). In the same sense, Muller and Chandon (2002) note the effect of waiting before the act of purchase and of evaluation after the act of purchase on the emotion of consumption. Thus, satisfaction appears in this sense as the consequence of a positive judgment with regard to the brand (Ndangwa, 2020). Also, the latter highlight four factors which influence the emotion of consumption, namely: the wait before the act of purchase, the previous experience, the perceived performance and the perceived disagreement. By analyzing the relationships between these factors, they note the conformity of positive emotion, but not that of negative emotion. Then, they deduce that relative to positive emotion, there is a significant relationship between consumption emotion, and perceived performance and perceived disagreement, which allows us to affirm that gratification is linked to consumption emotion. Also, positive emotion has a positive influence on consumer satisfaction and, conversely, negative emotion exerts a negative influence on consumption satisfaction (Oliver & Linda, 1991).

2. Research design and formulation of hypotheses

The review of the previous literature guided us on the conceptual framework retained. Especially since hypothetico-deductive research is not limited to simple theory (Errabi & Hamadi, 2023), to complete and nourish this theoretical reflection, we examined the practices of Cameroonian consumers. Thus, two studies allowed us to validate our research hypotheses. The exploratory phase of this research justifies the validity of our model and reassures our hypotheses. The figure below illustrates the proposed model reflecting the causal relationships between the variables.

Figure: Conceptual model of the research

Our work is based on the main hypothesis according to which brand personality in general would positively influence consumer satisfaction. Brand personality, like brand image, has long been considered a true precursor to consumer satisfaction (Hoeffler & Keller, 2020). According to Cindy & Lombart (2013), brand personality is considered by companies as a tool allowing them to achieve their objective of consumer satisfaction. Especially since the characteristics of a product influence the perception of the personality of the latter (Boucha, 2018). In addition, brand personality would have a significant indirect impact on consumer loyalty via their level of satisfaction with this brand, thereby creating a source of emotion (Rita & Valette-Florence, 2020). The verbatim extract from one of our interviewees below illustrates this point of view well: *[... Overall I am satisfied with Guinness since it manages to meet my expectations on a physical and nutritional level and I can drink Guinness without having eaten, I have no problem...]* (Respondent H, Male – 35 years old – Sales agent – License). Satisfaction is described as an emotion due to the significant power exerted by affects and emotions in consummatory and post-consummatory processes (Valette-Florence, 2017). Moreover, predominant positive emotions explain satisfaction with a brand (Rita & Valette-Florence, 2020; Becheur and al., 2017). Other examples in the automotive sector highlight “joy” or “love” (Huang & Jian, 2015; Becheur & al., 2017; Aaker, 1997; Lacoecilhe, 2000). In other words, this has a significant impact on the emotional dimension of the consumer (Aoufi., and al., 2021). In view of all of the above, it is therefore trivial to formulate the hypothesis according to which brand personality positively influences consumption emotion (H1). Another consequence of brand personality is gratification. Indeed, this concept of expectation linked to consumer satisfaction derives from the very popular model of the disconfirmation of expectations paradigm (Oliver, 1980), according to which it is important for the consumer to evaluate to what extent the product/service provides particular benefits or produces expected

performance. According to this paradigm, the consumer feels satisfaction to the extent that the actual performance of the product corresponds to or exceeds the level of expectation. Gratification therefore appears to be an important element of consumer engagement with a brand. Thus, the performance of the product as it is actually perceived by the consumer which is the basis of the formation of satisfaction (Cindy & Lombard, 2013). As part of this research, the gratification of the consumer's need for the brand will be understood as the evaluation of the attributes or characteristics obtained and used, as well as the benefits or ultimate values that the latter brings to them (Cindy & Lombard, 2013). In addition to this work, other researchers have postulated and verified direct links between satisfaction and other variables of the disconfirmation of expectations such as emotions (Rita & Valette-Florence, 2020), which are the direct determinants of the disconfirmation of expectations. consumer satisfaction. Thus, based on this research, we posit that there is a causal link between brand personality and gratification (H2).

3. Methodology

The main objective of our exploratory study is to better understand the connection that consumers establish with their favorite beverage brand. Thanks to the Sphinx IQ software, this first phase of our research ensures the consumer's knowledge of Guinness company drinks, their ability to make their choice in the world of drinks previously listed as well as the evaluation global Guinness products. It is carried out on a sample consisting of 27% women and 73% men obeying the principle of semantic saturation (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). The objective of choosing the preferred brand during these interviews was to determine the brand with the greatest notoriety among consumers. That is, in total 27% women and 73% men. Table 2 below gives the statistics relating to the different brands mentioned by the respondents.

Table N°2: Occurrence appearance

Brand	CP15R ¹		OA15R ²	
	Number	Frequency	Number	frequency
Malta Guinness	1	07,00%	1	01,45%
Guinness Smooth	3	20,00%	14	20,29%
Guinness ordinaire	10	67,00%	15	21,74%
Ice Black	0	00,00%	15	21,74%
Ice Red	0	00,00%	7	10,15%
Harpe	1	07,00%	12	17,39%
Orijin	0	00,00%	3	04,35%
Triple Black	0	00,00%	1	01,45%
Black Lable	0	00,00%	1	01,45%
Total	15	100,00%	69	100,00%

Source: Our care

Table 2 above demonstrates that ordinary Guinness, known under the popular name “Guinness”, is the preferred brand of this company’s consumers. In view of these statistics and our objectives, it is therefore trivial to note that the quantitative studies will only focus on this brand.

3.1. Measurement of variables, methods of analysis and psychometric qualities retained

The principal component analysis shows that with regard to brand personality, five dimensions are retained and two dimensions for satisfaction. In fact, the dimensions chosen are those which provide the maximum amount of expected information. Thus, the brand personality variable is understood using a set of 38 items relating to human personality measurement traits and are all evaluated on the 5-point Likert scale. We successively launched four PCAs before obtaining the factors that best explain the personality of the Guinness brand. Finally, the last analysis allowed us to obtain a barometer of the personality of the Guinness brand comprising five (05) dimensions which restore a total of 62.245% of the initial information with Reliability Statistics $0.697 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8$. The factors thus obtained were named: Factor 1 (*Guinness gives me a good*

¹ Brand consumption for 15 respondents

² Occurrence of appearance of the brand for 15 respondents

mood, unique, excellent) = Domination; *Factor2 (Who makes you strong, who makes you proud, who liberates)* = Expansiveness; *Factor 3 (Imaginative, creative, endearing)* = Creativity; *Factor 4 (Reassuring, efficient, innovative)* = Conscientious; *Factor 5 (Elegant, stylish)* = Pleasant. Satisfaction was measured using a set of seven items. Thus, we launched the principal component analysis twice in a row to obtain a single factor necessary to explain the phenomenon and restoring 61.674% of the expected information with acceptable internal reliability ($0.7 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8$). Finally, it emerges from this second PCA relevance test that the KMO index has a value of 0.804, considered good. Which means that PCA is relevant to our data. Likewise, Bartlett's test of sphericity of 432.629 at the significance level of 0.000 with reliability ($0.7 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8$). The first factor called F1 (*Consuming this brand is a good thing for me; I am happy with this brand; I am comfortable with the consumption of this brand ; It's a brand that gives me joy*) translates the emotion of consumption; and the second factor (*it gives me weight; I consider it a remedy*) corresponds to gratification. All of these factors restore a total of 61.476% of the initial information. After having carried out the exploratory factor analysis on the different items retained in this study, it is now appropriate to carry out the various analyzes of the existing links between the variables.

3.2. Test of the model and main results

It is important to remember that the objective of this analysis is to know whether Guinness brand personality really influences consumer satisfaction. This is a step-by-step analysis because the variable to be explained has two dimensions (gratification and emotion). Given the complexity and cumbersomeness of the analysis using structural equations, we opted for step-by-step regression. In order to study the different opportunities offered by the personality barometer in the context of brand management and more particularly the support of the relationship between the Guinness brand and gratification, we opted for the choice of multiple linear regression test the results of which are recorded in tables 3 and 4 below.

Table N°3: Summary of the regression model between brand personality and emotion
Quality indicators

	R	R²	R² Adjusted	F	Significance
Emotion	0,482	0,232	0,221	20,961	0,000

Coefficients

	Coeff. Stand. Bêta	T	Significance
Constante	2,309	0,000	0,976
Dimension : Domination	0,224	4,764	0,000
Dimension : expansiveness	0,189	4,019	0,000
Dimension : Créativité	0,297	6,303	0,000
Dimension : Conscientious	0,178	3,787	0,000
Dimension : Pleasant	0,162	3,448	0,000

Source : Our care

Table N°4: Summary of the regression model between brand personality and gratification

Quality indicators

	R	R²	R² Adjusted	F	Significance
Gratification	0,455	0,207	0,196	18,133	0,000

Coefficients

	Coeff. Stand. Bêta	T	Significance
Constante	0,030	0,000	1,000
Dimension : Domination	0,233	4,883	0,000
Dimension : expansiveness	0,341	7,143	0,000
Dimension : Créativité	-0,034	-0,704	0,482
Dimension : Conscientious	0,174	3,639	0,000
Dimension : Pleasant	0,069	1,436	0,152

Source : Our care

These tables show that brand personality helps explain 22.10% of the emotion and 19.6% of the gratification that consumers obtain from the Guinness brand. Which means that the relationships between these variables exist. In addition, the F test with regard to the coefficients of the model are respectively all significant: 20.961 (*for emotion*), 18.133 (*for gratification*) all significant at the threshold of 0.000. Thus, the predictive power of the brand personality barometer is clearly greater for emotion towards the brand than for gratification. Likewise, the analyzes finally demonstrate that not all dimensions of brand personality have the same impact on the two dimensions of satisfaction. Although all coefficients are greater than zero in explaining the link between brand personality and emotion, it turns out that the creative and pleasant dimensions do not have an important influence in explaining gratification. Moreover, even if this relationship existed, it would be negative for the creativity dimension. Furthermore,

in the analysis of the link between brand personality and emotion, creativity wins over the other dimensions of personality. The regression equations of these two models will be:

Equation1:

Emotion=2.309+0.304Dominance+0.243Expansiveness+0.330Creativity+0.427Conscientious+0.418Agreeable+ ϵ . With ϵ = Residue.

Equation2:

Gratification=0.030+0.359Dominance+0.400Expansiveness+0.330Creativity+0.368Conscientious+ 0.434Agreeable+ ϵ . With ϵ = Residue

Considering the coefficients of the model and the values of F which are respectively 163.957 (for gratification) and 152.654 (for emotion), at the threshold of 0.000. This leads us to conclude that the regression models fit the data very well.

4. Discussion of the results

The main objective of this research was to analyze the influence of brand personality on consumer satisfaction. Thus, thanks to spontaneous awareness tests, the Guinness brand was selected for this study. It appears that the Guinness brand has a positive influence on consumer satisfaction. The results of the tests by the multiple regression method attested that the personality of the Guinness brand positively influences consumer satisfaction. These results confirm those of Ferrandi et al. (2000) or the recent work of Rita and Pierre-Valette (2020). It is important to note, however, that brand personality is an important element of brand identity in the study of consumer behavior. However, the work carried out by Cindy and Didier L. (2010) also demonstrates that the personality of the Coca-Cola brand, which is well known among students, positively influences consumer choice.

Furthermore, the work of Aaker (1993) reveals that, for the eau de toilette and clothing market, dimensions of brand personality such as excitement and roughness seem relevant. In the context of this study, personality traits such as: confident, determined and intelligent from the first dimension refer to dominance. In other words, modern Guinness dominates this company's other drink brands. Furthermore, the traits (original, unique and excellent) of the second dimension of personality in the context of this research reflect sincerity. These traits were found to be more salient and more predictive of consumer satisfaction with the Guinness brand.

Considering the quality indicators and coefficients of this model, it is important to suggest that this company strengthen its brand strategy by relying more on these two dimensions.

Conclusion

The main objective of this research was to analyze the influence of brand personality on consumer satisfaction. Thus, as part of this research, we focused on the concept of brand personality through perspectives on the existing relationship between consumers and brands, as well as a certain number of references on human personality. and the applicability of the concept of personality to the domain of brands has been legitimized. Previous research reveals that the concept of brand personality is in line with work on animism (Sirgy, 1982). Thus, it appears that humans need to humanize objects in order to facilitate their interaction with the immaterial world. Consequently, consumers have no difficulty understanding brands as real people (Aaker, 1993). However, researchers agree regarding the definition of personality: “Brand personality can then be defined as “all the human personality traits associated with the brand”. As part of this research, we mainly focused on understanding the perceived personality of the Guinness brand and not the consumer personality of the Guinness brand. From this perspective, it appears that it corresponds to a facet of the brand image and that, the domination and sincerity were found to be the most determining factors of Guinness brand personality. Indeed, the latter bring together all the associations attached to this brand, some of which are in fact real human personality traits.

Thus, this research from a theoretical point of view proposes the following definition: “set of human personality traits exceptionally transposable to brands”. The exceptional character in this definition that we propose refers to the fact that the brand subject to the study should have a high reputation because it is above all a question of traits relating to the human personality. Thus, only a few items truly relating to the domain of personality should be included in brand personality measurement scales.

Furthermore, items identified within the framework of this study allowed us to adapt a scale to the Cameroonian context and precisely that of the drinks sector. Exploratory studies with consumers were conducted to produce a large list of adjectives applicable to brands assuming they are considered real people. Based on thirty-eight items measuring human personality, the purification of this list made it possible to select only the adjectives relevant to the concept of personality in the Cameroonian context. The latter is organized around two dimensions: Domination and Sincerity. Thus, as part of this research, we proposed a barometer for measuring the personality of the Guinness brand.

On an operational level, the results of several studies have highlighted the predictive power of brand personality on consumer satisfaction. It turns out that this power varies depending on product categories and brands. More precisely, the results of this research demonstrate that not all dimensions of personality have the same influence on satisfaction.

Furthermore, it is important to note that from a managerial point of view, it turns out that the brand personality barometer makes it possible to very precisely differentiate brands on the basis of their personality profile, including for brands belonging to the same product category. New analyzes should notably make it possible to refine the issue of brand personality. Likewise, it seems relevant to deepen the results concerning the influence of brand personality on consumer behavior while integrating the moderating role of price as well as the congruent effect between brand personality and that of the consumer. The results of this research enrich the understanding of the process by which the personality of a brand conditions the behavior of individuals. However, certain results require further investigation and open up new perspectives for studies, some of which are presented as part of this research.

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